

INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT RATES OF PHOSPHORUS AND POTASSIUM FERTILIZER APPLICATION ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF COWPEA (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) VARIETIES

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the influence of rates of phosphorus (p) and potassium (K) fertilizers on the growth and yield of two cowpea varieties (IT10k-863-11) and IT81D-1228-14) for two consecutive cropping seasons (2020 and 2021). Three rates of p (0, 20, 30kg/ha P₂O₅) and four rates of K (0, 20, 30, 40kg/ha K₂O) were utilized. The experimental design was a 2 x 3 x 4 factorial arrangement in randomized complete block replicated three times. Result indicated that leaf area index (LAI) at four weeks after sowing (LAI) at four weeks after sowing (4 WAS) in 2020, significantly (p<0.05) increased as p rates increased. However, at 10 and 12 WAS in 2020 and 2021 leaf area index (LAI) significantly (p<0.05) increased with 20kg/ha P₂O₅, but reduced at 30kg/ha P₂O₅ application. In both cropping seasons, 30 and 40kg/ha produced similar but highest LAI at 4, 8 and 10 WAS. Interaction of P and K demonstrated that at 4 WAS application of only 30kg/ha K₂O without P gave highest LAI (0.09 and 0.09) in both cropping seasons. All the yield parameters progressively increased as rates of K increased. Highest number of fresh pods/plant and seeds/pod, heaviest fresh pods per plant and as well as seed yield were associated with 40kg/ha K₂O application in both cropping seasons. The application of 40kg/ha K₂O with no application of P also produced better yield and yield attributes of the cowpea, hence 40kg/ha K₂O application without P was recommended for sustainable cowpea production in the Northern Guinea agro-ecological zone of Nigeria, especially when the soil has high available p (above the critical p level of 7mg/kg recommended for cowpea production).

Keywords: Cowpea, Fertilizer rates, Phosphorus, Potassium, growth and Yield

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) is a good source of dietary protein. It is utilized for human consumption, where the young leaves and immature pods are eaten as vegetables (Dugje *et al.*, 2009). According to FAOSTAT (2016), cowpea was grown on an estimated 12.3 million ha in Africa in 2014 with the bulk of production occurring on 10.6 million ha in West Africa, particularly in Nigeria, Niger, Burkina Faso, Mali, and Senegal (Eiana and Zelalem, 2020). All the plant parts that are used for food are nutritious, providing protein,

vitamins and minerals. Even though cowpea, a leguminous crop has the ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. It requires a starter dose of nitrogen for early growth and establishment (Udoh *et al.*, 2005). International Institute of Tropical Agriculture IITA (1982), submitted that it is adapted and capable of seed production in the strongly leached ultisols and oxisols of the humid tropics. Many cowpea varieties such as IT10k-863-11; IT14k-2115; IT84E; IT84E-124; II84E-108 and IT845-22-4 and vita-5 have been developed in Nigeria to suit the different ecological zones and

consumers taste (Remison, 2012; Udoh *et al.*; 2005). A range of high yielding seed type, dual purpose cowpea cultivars combining resistance to major pests, drought tolerance, erect, semi-erect type and early maturity have been developed (Remison, 2012; Turk *et al.*; 2006).

Uguru, (2011); Udoh *et al.*; (2005) reported that improved cultivars may yield up to 2500kg/ha within 0-70 days compared with less than 1000kg/ha seed yield of the local varieties which mature in 100-140 days (Zamir *et al.*; (2011), Naim and Jabereldar, (2010). The period of pod filling for cowpea is relatively short, about 17 to 24 days (Ano and Ubochi, 2008); Naim and Jabereldar, (2010). Flowering and pod filling is about 35-70 days for cowpea planted Mid-may and mid-june, from mid-june to late July and mid-July to late August respectively (Zamir *et al.*, 2011; Okaka *et al.*; 2002). In spite of the introduction of improved varieties, the grain yield of cowpea in Nigeria is still as low as 200-400kg/ha (Okeleye *et al.*, 2001). This low yield is due to poor management, pests and diseases (Remison, 2012). It is necessary to increase the crop yield in the country due to its great importance.

In the cropping system of Nigeria, Nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium need to be replenished in the soil more regularly than any other nutrients (El-Azzouni, 2007). Phosphorus, although not required in large quantities is critical to cowpea yield because of its multiple effect on nutrition and nitrogen fixation (Muleba and Godwin, 2005). It also influences the content of other nutrients in cowpea leaves (Kingsley and Natty, 2013) and seed (Olatunji and Olaoye, 2006). Application of 40-70kg/ha P_2O_5 in low fertility soils was recommended by Okeleye *et al.*, (2006). Potassium helps to overcome the moisture stress experienced by crops (Geetha and Varughese, 2001). Potassium fertilizer at 20kg/ha K_2O gave maximum fresh pod yield of cowpea (Geetha and Varughese, 2001), in order to achieve maximum benefit in fertilizer management, it is most essential to apply them at the right time, place and amount (Fixen and Reetz, 2006). Against this background, the

objective of this study was to determine the appropriate rates of P and K for optimum growth and yield of two cowpea varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field trial was conducted in 2020 and 2021 rainy season in the teaching and research farm of the institute for Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria (IAR/ABU) ($11^{\circ}11'N$ and $7^{\circ}38'E$) situated in the Northern Guinea Savannah ecological zone of Nigeria. Soil samples were collected at the depth of 0-30cm at the experiment site (Teaching and Research Farm before sowing and the soil samples were analyzed for physical and chemical properties following the procedures outlined by Agbaine, (1995).

Treatment and Experimental Design

The experimental design was 2 x 3 x 4 factorial in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. Two varieties of cowpea IT81D-122-14 erect and IT10k-63-11 semi erect type, three levels of phosphorus fertilizer (0, 20, 30, P_2O_5 kg/ha and four levels of potassium fertilizers (0, 20, 30 and 40 K_2O kg/ha) the cowpea seeds used were obtained from International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Ibadan, Nigeria. The potassium fertilizer was potassium nitrate (K_2O) while the phosphorus fertilizer was single super phosphate (P_2O_5).

Sowing and Cultural Practices

The gross plot was 5.0 x 3.0m, while the distance between plots was 0.5m. The distance between one replicate and the other was 1m. Planting spacing was 0.7m x 0.5m, giving a population of 28,571 stands per hectare and total land area of 30.6m x 15m ($483m^2$ or 0.0484/ha). Before sowing, the research site was mechanically ploughed and harrowed, and sowing was conducted on the first week of June 2020 and 2021 rainy season on flat. Two to three seeds per hole were sown, and were later thinned to one plant per stand, at about 9-13 days after sowing (DAS) (Fininsa, 1997), depending on the vigour of germination and growth vacant stands were supplied between 4-

7 days after sowing. Weeding was done twice before fertilizer application at three weeks after sowing (3 Week) and at flowering, eight weeks after sowing (8 WAS) (Olasanta and Aina, 1987). Blanket application of 20kg N/ha in the form of urea was incorporated into the soil to boost vegetative growth and establishment, through enhanced nodulation and atmospheric nitrogen fixation (Akpan, 2014). Phosphorus and potassium fertilizer were applied using ring method. The cowpea was sprayed with cypermethrin at the rate of 80g/1.5L of water after the formation of flower bud to control pest (Omotunde, 1996).

Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection was from three randomly selected plants in the middle rows in each plot (Muoneke *et al.*, 2013). Growth data included leaf area, leaf area index and vine length collected at 4, 8, 10 and 12 weeks after sowing (WAS). Three leaves were sampled per plant at the upper, middle and base portions and leaf area determined by multiplying the length and width of the sample leaves with the total number of leaves and a constant of 2.325 (Osei-yeboah *et al.*, 1983). Vine length was measured with a metre tape rule. Fresh pods were picked every 4 to 6 days depending on the frequency of podding. The number of fresh pods per plant and number of seeds per pod were counted while fresh pod weight per plant was determined by weighing the fresh pods harvested from three sampled cowpea plants per plot. Hundred (100) seed weight was determined by weighing 100 dried seeds per plot. Number of fresh pods/plant was determined by counting total fresh pods from three sampled stands and the total divided by three, while seed yield/ha⁻¹ was determined based on this formula: Grain Yield/Plot X 10,000cm².

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) according to Obi (1986) for factorial experiment in a randomized

complete block design. Fisher's least significant difference (F-LSD) at 5% probability level (Gomez and Gomez 1984) was adopted to compare the means.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Physical and chemical properties of the soil before sowing

Table 1 presented the result of physical and chemical properties of the soil prior to sowing. The texture of the soil was sandy loam and was slightly acidic (5.40 and 6.10) for 2020 and 2021 respectively. The total nitrogen was low while the available P was moderate considering Northern Guinea Savannah agro-ecological zone (Abdullahi and Lal, 1997; Singh *et al.*, 2000). However, with respect to cowpea production, the available P in the experimental site was higher than the critical level of P(7mg/ka) recommended for cowpea production. The basic cations were relatively low and the base saturation was moderate.

Table 1: Physicochemical Properties soil 0-30cm at Experimental Site in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons

Soil Properties	2020	2021
Particle Size (g/kg)		
Sand	130	110
Silt	150	140
Clay	720	750
Chemical Properties		
P ^H (H ₂ O; 1: 2: 5: (w/v)	5.40	6.10
P ^H (0.01M CaCl ₂ ; 2.5 (w/v)	6.20	6.60
Exchange Acidity (Cmol/kg soil)	0.05	0.06
	0.07	0.09
Electrical Conductivity (mg/kg)		
Organic Carbon (g/kg)	5.10	7.53
Total N (g/kg)	0.18	0.31
Available P (mg/kg)	10.96	11.82
Exchangeable Cations (Cmol/kg)		
K (C mol/kg)	0.17	0.22
Ca (C mol/kg)	4.28	5.75
Mg (C mol/kg)	0.49	0.85
Na (C mol/kg)	0.21	0.28
CEC K (C mol/kg)	5.75	6.55
Extract Mirco Nutrients (C mol/kg)		
Zinc Zn	5.13	5.33
Sodium Adsorption Ration (SAR)	0.04	0.06
Parent Base Saturation (PBS)	85.30	87.85

Source: Soil samples analysis at the Soil Department, Institute for Agriculture Research IAR/ABU, Zaria

Leaf area and vine length as influenced by rates of phosphorus, potassium and varieties in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons

Table 2 the leaf area index of the varieties were not statistically different ($P > 0.05$) between the varieties at four weeks after sowing (4 WAS) in both 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons. However, the variety IT8ID-1228-14 had

higher leaf area index at 12 WAS in 2020, and 8 and 10 WAS in 2021, than IT10K-863-11. The varying performance of the two varieties was due to their genetic composition. Sana *et al.*, (2003); Tsegeye *et al.*, (2007) who reported similar differences in other crops and ascribed it to genetic and environmental factors.

In 2020 cropping season, P effect on LAI was not significant at 4, 8 and 10 WAS but was

significant only at 12 WAS. The LAI significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased with 20kg/ha P_2O_5 but reduced at 30kg/ha P_2O_5 application. In 2021, the P effect on LAI was only significant at 8 and 10 WAS. The LAI result followed the same trend as was observed in 2020. The rate 20kg/ha P_2O_5 may represent the optimal level needed at this stage of growth and development. Similarly, there was a significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in the leaf area as K rates increased at 4, 8, 10 and 12 WAS in

2020 and 2021 (Only at 8 and 12 WAS). This implied that early leaf development could be influenced greater availability of P and K. previous works (Geetha and Varughese, 2001; Owolade *et al.*, 2006) reported increased leaf area index with increase in P and K singly. Both 30 and 40kg/ha K_2O produced similar but highest LAI at 4, 8 and 10 WAS in both cropping seasons.

Table 2: Leaf area index and vine length of cowpea as influenced by rates of phosphorus, potassium and variety in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons

IT10k-863-11	Leaf area index (LAI)				Vine length (cm)					
	2020				2021					
	4 WAS	8 WAS	10 WAS	12 WAS	4 WAS	8 WAS	10 WAS	12 WAS	8 WAS	10 WAS
Veg. cowpea variety	0.074	0.615	0.633	0.388	0.078	0.590	0.626	0.389	55.8	55.7
IT10k - 863	0.072	0.682	0.689	0.414	0.077	0.704	0.702	0.413	46.8	47.3
IT8ID-1228-14	ns	ns	ns	0.09	ns	0.06	0.05	ns	ns	ns
LSD _{0.05}										
Phosphorus rate (kg/ha)	0.071	0.612	0.603	0.378	0.076	0.624	0.615	0.379	50.8	5.01
	0.072	0.690	0.711	0.431	0.075	0.679	0.707	0.422	52.6	51.6
	0.076	0.614	0.670	0.393	0.082	0.647	0.671	0.960	50.5	51.2
LSD _{0.05}	ns	ns	ns	0.02	ns	0.06	0.05	ns	ns	ns
Potassium rate (kg/ha)	0.065	0.555	0.565	0.345	0.073	0.576	0.620	0.348	53.4	53.0
	0.070	0.613	0.663	0.428	0.075	0.619	0.634	0.430	49.5	51.0
	0.078	0.650	0.686	0.419	0.081	0.669	0.683	0.414	51.2	51.0
	0.076	0.776	0.731	0.411	0.081	0.724	0.720	0.411	51.2	51.0
LSD _{0.05}	0.01	0.07	0.07	0.02	ns	0.09	ns	0.03	ns	ns

WAS = Week after sowing ns = non-significant

Interactive effect of phosphorus and potassium on leaf area index LAI at 4 and 12 WAS

Table 3 the interaction of P and K demonstrated that at 4 WAS, application of only 30kg/ha K_2O without P gave highest LAI (0.089) and 0.091) in both cropping season. However, at 12 WAS the combined application of 20kg/ha P_2O_5 and 20kg/ha K_2O enhanced highest LAI (0.484 and 0.485) in both cropping season. Generally, there was a decline in LAI after 10 WAS. This was due to the maturity and senescence of the crop.

At 8 and 10 WAS in 2021, longer vine was significantly higher for semi-erect, IT10K-863-11 in both years than for IT81D-1228-14, the erect variety (Table 2). The vine length did not differ among the P and K rates in both years. The vine length ranged from 51.cm to 52.cm and 54.3cm to 54.9cm with P application in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons, respectively, the vine length range from 51cm to 53cm and 53cm to 54.7cm at 10 WAS, with K application.

Table 3: Interaction effect of phosphorus and potassium to leaf area index (LAI) at 4 and 12 WAS in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons

Phosphorus rate (kg/ha)	Potassium rate (kg/ha)	2020		2021	
		4WAS	12WAS	4WAS	12WAS
0	0	0.042	0.276	0.056	0.301
	20	0.072	0.367	0.072	0.346
	30	0.089	0.454	0.091	0.456
	40	0.079	0.417	0.083	0.412
20	0	0.068	0.394	0.070	0.374
	20	0.072	0.484	0.075	0.485
	30	0.067	0.405	0.075	0.399
	40	0.083	0.441	0.079	0.452
30	0	0.084	0.365	0.092	0.368
	20	0.077	0.435	0.079	0.459
	30	0.78	0.398	0.076	0.387
	40	0.067	0.376	0.079	0.371
LSD _{0.05}		0.05	0.04	0.02	0.05

Yield and component of Cowpea

Table 4 the erect (IT81D-1228-4 variety produced significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher number of fresh pods (19.96), heavier pods per plant (50.68g) and hectare (14.48kg/ha) than the semi-erect (IT10K-863-11) variety in 2021. But in 2020, the number of fresh, number of fresh pods, weight of fresh pods and fresh pod yield did not significantly ($P < 0.05$) differ between the two varieties. This explained the difference in genetic constituents of the two cowpea varieties. Earlier work (Nwofia, 2012) on the performance of several varieties indicated that IT81D-1228-14 was among the high yielding varieties.

There was a progressive increase in all the yield attributes ($P < 0.05$) as the rates of potassium increased. In other words, the highest K rate (40kg/ha K_2O) was attributed with highest number of fresh pods/plant and seeds/pod; heaviest fresh pods per plant and as well as seed yield, in both cropping season.

Table 5 the status of K in the experimental site was relatively low which explained why the varieties responded to K application with respect to yield attributes. However, different rates of P did not have significant influence on the yield attributes of cowpea in both cropping seasons. This was surprising as one expected to observe a significant response of cowpea with the application of different P levels. The critical soil available P level specifically for cowpea production is 7mg/kg (Kang and Nangju, 1983). In 2020, available P was 10.96mg/kg for 0-30cm depth while it was 11.82mg/kg in 2021, respectively (Table 1). Phosphorus, although not required in large quantities, is critical to cowpea yield because of its multiple effects on nutrition (Muleba and Ezumah, 1985). Probably, the P rates used in this study were not much.

Table 4: Number, weight of fresh pods and fresh pod yield of cowpea as influenced by rate of phosphorus, Potassium and variety in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons

Veg. cowpea variety	2020			2021		
	No. of fresh pods/plant	Wt. of fresh pods/plant (g)	Fresh pod yield (t/ha)	No. of fresh pods/plant	Wt. of fresh pods/plant (g)	
IT10k-863-II	19.74	51.27	14.65	18.15	44.10	
IT8ID-1228-14	96.95	51.56	14.73	19.96	50.68	
LSD _{0.05}	ns	ns	ns	0.78	2.99	
Phosphorus rate (kg/ha)						
0	19.46	51.81	14.80	18.47	48.59	
20	19.85	50.76	14.50	19.01	46.53	
30	20.24	51.68	14.77	19.68	47.06	
LSD _{0.05}	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	
Potassium rate (kg/ha)						
0	16.91	48.40	13.83	16.67	40.65	
20	19.59	48.11	13.75	18.74	44.83	
30	20.50	49.53	14.15	19.48	47.61	
40	22.39	59.61	17.03	21.33	56.48	
LSD _{0.05}	1.36	4.96	1.42	1.09	4.23	

Table 5: Number of seeds/pod, 100-seed weight and seed yield of cowpea an influenced by rates of phosphorus, potassium and variety in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons

Veg. cowpea variety	2020			2021		
	No. of seeds/pod	100-seed weight (g)	Seed yield (kg/ha)	No. of seeds /pod	100-seed weight (g)	Seed yield (kg/ha)
IT10k-863-11	14.08	9.68	255.3	14.09	9.64	255.3
IT8ID-1228-14	13.97	10.01	388.1	13.87	9.96	388.1
LSD _{0.05}	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Phosphorus rate (kg/ha)						
0	13.85	9.97	37.13	13.99	9.82	37.13
20	13.90	9.98	371.3	14.02	9.83	371.3
30	14.17	9.76				
LSD _{0.05}	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Potassium rate (kg/ha)						
0	13.69	9.27	2853	13.43	9.06	2853
20	13.73	10.07	358.2	13.70	9.97	358.2
30	13.51	10.16	347.2	13.74	10.09	347.2
40	14.97	9.88	496.2	15.00	9.93	496.2
LSD _{0.05}	0.78	0.02	48.01	0.72	0.40	48.01

Interactive effect of phosphorus and potassium to some yield and yield components of cowpea in 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons

Table 6 and 7, the result of P and K interaction showed that the application of 40kg/ha K₂O with zero combination of P enhanced the production of highest number of fresh pods, heaviest fresh pods and fresh pod yield per hectare in both cropping seasons. The heaviest 100-seeds and seed yield per hectare in 2020 were produced when 20kg/ha K₂O and 0kg/ha

P₂O₅. Th was applied. A sharp decrease in number of fresh pods per plant and fresh pod yield per hectare in both cropping seasons was observed with the application of either 30 or 40kg/ha K₂O with 0kg/ha P₂O₅. The implication is that the application of higher rate of K (30 or 40kg/ha K₂O) with-out P, especially in a soil that has high available P (more than the critical level 7mg/kg for cowpea production) will enhance higher fresh pod, seed and dry matter yields of cowpea. Under this condition, little or no cost will be directed to P fertilizer acquisition.

Table 6: Interaction effect of phosphorus and potassium to some yield and yield components of cowpea in 2020

Phosphorus rate(kg/ha)	Potassium rate(kg/ha)	No. of fresh pod/plant	Wt.of fresh pod/plant	Fresh pod yield kg/ha	No. of seeds/pod	100-seed weight (g)	Seed yield kg/ha
0	0	12.8	42.5	12.2	13.4	8.5	242.85
	20	19.1	46.9	13.4	13.2	10.6	302.85
	30	20.8	52.3	14.9	13.8	10.0	285.71
	40	25.2	65.4	18.7	14.9	10.1	288.57
20	0	18.4	47.2	13.5	13.9	9.4	268.57
	20	19.7	49.1	14.0	13.9	9.9	282.85
	30	19.4	49.9	13.3	13.0	10.3	294.28
	40	21.9	53.1	17.3	14.8	10.4	297.14
30	0	19.6	48.4	15.8	13.8	9.3	282.85
	20	20.1	48.1	13.8	14.1	9.7	277.14
	30	21.2	49.5	14.3	13.7	10.2	291.42
	40	20.1	59.6	15.2	15.5	9.2	262.85
LSD _{0.05}		2.36	8.59	2.43	ns	0.40	43.7

Table 7: Interaction effect of phosphorus and potassium to some yield and yield components of cowpea in 2021

Phosphorus rate(kg/ha)	Potassium rate (kg/ha)	No. of fresh pod/plant	Wt. of fresh pod/plant	Fresh pod yield kg/ha	No. of seeds/pod	100- seed weight (g)	Seed yield kg/ha
0	0	11.4	30.5	8.7	13.3	8.4	240.00
	20	18.1	43.7	12.5	13.6	10.6	302.85
	30	20.7	49.6	14.2	13.9	9.9	282.85
	40	23.7	70.6	20.2	15.2	10.4	297.14
20	0	17.8	43.3	12.4	13.7	9.3	282.85
	20	19.4	44.5	12.7	13.8	9.5	271.42
	30	18.6	46.7	13.3	13.5	10.3	294.28
	40	20.3	1.7	14.8	15.1	10.3	294.28
30	0	20.8	48.1	13.8	13.3	9.5	271.42
	20	18.8	48.3	13.2	13.8	9.9	285.71
	30	19.2	46.6	13.3	13.9	10.1	288.56
	40	19.6	47.2	13.5	14.8	9.2	262.85
LSD _{0.05}		1.90	7.32	2.09	ns	0.70	ns

CONCLUSION

The study showed that growth and yield of cowpea responded better to K application than P. Increase in K application progressively increased the leaf area index, vine length as well as fresh pod and seed yields of the crop. It was recommended that farmers should apply 40kg.ha K₂O with no application of P, to ensure better yield and yield attributes of cowpea,

especially in a soil that has high concentration of available P above the critical level. However, 40kg/ha K₂O may not necessarily be the optimum level under the condition of high available P for the production of cowpea. This is because the increment of K₂O rate will increase the performance of the cowpea.

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